

Received: 14 October 2022

Revised: 19 November 2022

Accepted: 17 December 2022

DOI:

Research Article

Post Covid-19 Paradigm Shift in Social Sciences, Technology and Public Health in Nigeria

Dr ADETOLA, Olugbenga¹ | Dr Akindamola, Saheed² | Popoola-Adebayo, Maryam¹ |

Dr Fogbonjaiye, Seun Samuel³ |

¹School of Management and Business Studies
Department of Banking and Finance
Yaba College of Technology, Yaba,
Lagos
Nigeria

²Saheed-Matic Research Solutions
Nigeria

³Department of Economics
Southwestern University Nigeria,
Ogun State
Nigeria

Correspondence

Dr ADETOLA, Olugbenga
Email: adetolaolugbenga@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic has altered the business world in unprecedented and historic ways, the effects of which have been felt the world over. As the new reality of the pandemic sets in, organizations and individuals grapple with the implications of the virus on technology, public health and social humanity. The difficulty comes in assessing paradigm shifts and the long-term implications of the pandemic. A paradigmatic shift is a fundamental change in the underlying assumptions of a phenomenon. This necessitated the study ascertain the post covid-19 paradigm shift in social sciences, technology and public health in Nigeria. A systematic search of published literatures on covid-19 pandemic and the changes that have taken place in the social phenomenon was examined. Published peer review journals, abstracts, Gray literature (technical reports, government documents, reports, etc.), inaugural lectures, and internet articles were reviewed. Manual search of reference lists of selected articles were checked for further relevant studies. The review showed that the COVID-19 pandemic has created multiple paradigm shifts the likes of which organizations have never before seen. Even the most prepared organizations scrambled to react to the rapid changes brought on by the pandemic. Whereas most organizations would agree that technology, public health, social sciences and humanity such as (financial consequences, remote work, worker well-being, and career attitudes) have all shifted, organizations ability to understand and respond to those shifts in both the short- and long-term has become another story altogether. It is recommended that the government should grant tax breaks to companies seeking to increase their capacity to produce import substitute goods, which could even mean zero-rating VAT for the next 3-months; Releasing VAT refunds to assist businesses with managing their cash flow.

Keywords: post covid-19, paradigm shift, social sciences, technology, public health

Copyright: 2023 by the authors. Licensee KMF Publishers (www.kmf-publishers.com). This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

BACKGROUND

The COVID-19 pandemic has altered the business world in unprecedented and historic ways, the effects of which have been felt the world over. As the new reality of the pandemic sets in, organizations and individuals grapple with the implications of the virus (Akindamola, 2020). In the short-term, organizations have generally engaged in empathic pro-employee responses, and many have radically altered how and where employees work. At face value, both actions seem both reasonable and prudent. The difficulty comes in assessing paradigm shifts and the long-term implications of the pandemic. A paradigmatic shift is a fundamental change in the underlying assumptions of a phenomenon. In research, these are rare but impactful shifts that radically change our understanding of phenomena by altering the foundational assumptions upon which our understanding is derived (Antara, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic has the potential to result in multiple paradigm shifts, the spectrum of shifts range from personal to professional, individual to organizational, and across most industries. The world is at its most interdependent economically and has never faced this level of comprehensive interruption. Whereas the short-term effects have been felt and recognized by many, resulting paradigm shifts caused by the pandemic will likely have long-term effects of unknown scope and impact (IMF, 2020). Many are adjusting to novel organizational demands of the pandemic while hoping for a swift “return to normal.” In time, the implications of these demands may not only shift but have a lasting effect on the way organizations and employees function, resulting in a “new normal (Loayza & Pennings, 2020).”

Initially, most individuals and organizations seemed to maintain a generally positive outlook on the situation. The need to rely on unemployment was serving its purpose as temporary assistance that would soon become unnecessary once the pandemic reached its peak and allowed workers to return to the status quo (ILO, 2020). However, even with most

stay-at-home orders expiring around the country, the pandemic continued to delay many individuals’ ability to return to work. Whereas some industries have begun to rebound, rather than a simple return to the status quo, the recovery will be driven more by consumer behavior and demand than by a simple desire to return to normalcy (Antara, 2020). Indeed, many industries such as travel, entertainment, and restaurants continue to suffer as the pandemic draws on (World Bank, 2020).

Observation revealed by scholars that pandemic such as SARS, Ebola among others have overtime affected the world economy, in which African countries are not an exemption. Indeed, the emergence of COVID-19 and its increasing incidence focusing on the Nigeria economy has called for drastic review and changes in the earlier revenue expectations and fiscal projections (UNESCO, 2020). The recent global crash in oil prices, fuelled by an OPEC price war and subsequent drop in demand of oil derivatives amid COVID-19 containment measures worldwide, resulted in so many oil producing countries reducing its oil production and exports including West African countries. However, depletion of foreign reserves in the West African countries Central Bank (normally countries get foreign currency from exports to replenish their reserves) has made it difficult to stabilise the local currency (Naira) against the US dollar, causing a rapid depreciation of the Naira. Depreciation of the Naira did not seem to have an immediate impact on inflation (Petroleum Economist 24/03/2020). However, prices of essential goods have risen, mainly caused by decreased trade following movement restrictions and lockdowns at global level. Higher transaction costs for trade of essential goods caused by prolonged movement restrictions and continued currency devaluation, following the global decline of oil prices, will likely result in a continued increase in prices and decreased households’ purchasing power (Mahler, Lanker, Aguilar & Wu, 2020). Over the long-term, the crash in oil prices may lead to a continued reduction of the government’s budget (normally based on anticipated earnings from

oil production), reduced government revenues and foreign exchange reserves, with the risk of economic fallout (Peerii et al., 2020). This would make it increasingly challenging for many African countries to borrow money from financial institutions, due to lenders' doubt on their inability to repay. The impact on financing flows risks pose a reduction in the government's ability to finance health and safety net programmes in response to the pandemic (Akindamola, 2020).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The lockdowns across countries have entailed a rise in the use of information systems and networks, with massive changes in usage patterns and usage behaviour. Employees are adjusting to new "normals" - with meetings going completely online, office work shifting to the home, with new emerging patterns of work. These changes have come across most organizations, whether in business, society, or government. The changes have also come suddenly, with barely any time for organizations and people to plan for, prepare and implement new setups and arrangements; they have had to adjust, try, experiment, and find ways that did not exist before. The outbreak of coronavirus disease-2019 (COVID-19) has shown to severely affect national and global economies. Various enterprises are facing different issues with a certain degree of losses. Particularly, enterprises are facing a variety of problems such as a decrease in demand, supply chain disruptions, cancellation of export orders, raw material shortage, and transportation disruptions, among others. Nevertheless, it is quite clear that enterprises around the globe are experiencing the significant impact of COVID-19 outbreak on their businesses. The major victims of COVID-19 outbreak are organizations in the developing countries including the government agencies because they do not possess sufficient resources, especially financial and managerial, and are not prepared for such disruptions likely to go longer than expected (Rahman & Matin, 2020).

According to AfDB 2020, as a result of the pandemic, growth in the West Africa region, will stand at 4.0 percent in 2020, following growth of 3.6 percent in 2019, and as result of the global pandemic is now projected to contract by -2.0 percent in 2020, and could fall by as much as -4.3 percent in a worst-case scenario. Countries that depend on oil and tourism for foreign exchange and fiscal revenues will especially face reduced fiscal space and heightened external account imbalances, stoking a build-up of public debt. However, the government of Nigeria must lead economic diversification drive. It is one practicable way to saddle through the current economic uncertainties and instabilities. What the consequences of COVID-19 pandemic should further offer the economy of Nigerian states and policymakers, is that the one-tracked, monolithic reliance on oil is failing. Diversification priorities to alternative sectors such as agriculture, solid minerals, manufacturing and services sectors, were not intensified by the government, due to lack of patriotisms (Akindamola, 2020). It is against this background that the research seeks to investigate the Post Covid-19 Paradigm Shift in Social Sciences, Technology and Public Health in Nigeria.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The aim of the study is to investigate the Post Covid-19 Paradigm Shift in Social Sciences, Technology and Public Health in Nigeria. The specific objectives were:

- To examine the effect of covid-19 spread rate on social changes in Nigeria
- To ascertain the effect of covid-19 spread rate on changes in technology usage in Nigeria
- To investigate the effect of covid-19 spread rate on changes in public health in Nigeria

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section dwells on the conceptual framework, theoretical framework and empirical literature review.

Concepts of Covid-19 Pandemic

Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) is an RNA virus, with a typical crown-like appearance under an electron microscope due to the presence of glycoprotein spikes on its envelope. It is not the first time that a coronavirus causing an epidemic has been a significant global health threat: in November 2019, an outbreak of corona-viruses (CoVs) with severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS)-CoV started in the Chinese province of Guangdong and again, in September 2012 the Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS)-CoV appeared (Hsu, Chia & Lim, 2020). There are four genera of CoVs: (I) α -coronavirus (alphaCoV), (II) β -coronavirus (betaCoV) probably present in bats and rodents, while (III) δ -coronavirus (deltaCoV), and (IV) γ -coronavirus (gammaCoV) probably represent avian species (World Health Organization, 2020).

Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) is defined as illness caused by a novel coronavirus now called severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2; formerly called 2019-nCoV), which was first identified amid an outbreak of respiratory illness cases in Wuhan City, Hubei Province, China. It was initially reported to the WHO on December 31, 2019. On January 30, 2020, the WHO declared the COVID-19 outbreak a global health emergency (Lu, Stratton & Tang, 2020). On March 11, 2020, the WHO declared COVID-19 a global pandemic, its first such designation since declaring H1N1 influenza a pandemic in 2009 (World Health Organization, 2020).

Illness caused by SARS-CoV-2 was termed COVID-19 by the WHO, the acronym derived from "coronavirus disease 2019." The name was chosen to avoid stigmatizing the virus's origins in terms of populations, geography, or animal associations. Covid-19 is put as a patient with acute respiratory illness (fever and at least one sign/symptom of respiratory disease, e.g., cough, shortness of breath), AND a history of travel to or residence in a location

reporting community transmission of COVID-19 disease during the 14 days prior to symptom onset; ORB (World Health Organization, 2020). The virus has a natural and zoonotic origin: two scenarios that can plausibly explain the origin of SARS-CoV2 are: (i) natural selection in an animal host before zoonotic transfer; and (ii) natural selection in humans following zoonotic transfer. Clinical features and risk factors are highly variable, making the clinical severity range from asymptomatic to fatal. Understanding of COVID-19 is on-going. This review aims to summarize early findings on the epidemiology, clinical features, diagnosis, management, and prevention of COVID-19 (Lipsitch, 2020).

The COVID-19 epidemic expanded in early December from Wuhan, China's 7th most populous city, throughout China and was then exported to a growing number of countries. The first confirmed case of COVID-19 outside China was diagnosed on 13th January 2020 in Bangkok (Thailand). On the 2nd of March 2020, 67 territories outside mainland China had reported 8565 confirmed cases of COVID-19 with 132 deaths, as well as significant community transmission occurring in several countries worldwide, including Iran and Italy and it was declared a global pandemic by the WHO on the 11th of March 2020. The number of confirmed cases is constantly increasing worldwide and after Asian and European regions, a steep increase in cases is currently (31 March 2020) being observed in low-income countries (Letko, Marzi & Munster, 2020).

Concepts of Paradigm Shift

The term paradigm shift refers to a major change in the worldview, concepts, and practices of how something works or is accomplished. A paradigm shift can happen within a wide variety of contexts from scientific research to industry (Janet & Ngugi, 2014). Paradigm shifts in industry often happen when new technology is introduced that radically alters the production process or manufacturing of a good or service. These shifts are key drivers in many of the

processes that a society undergoes, such as the American Industrial Revolution or the information revolution since the 2000s. Paradigm shift is a perception or a group of ideas about how things should be done, made, or thought about. In other words, it's the perspective on the world, subjective point of view, or beliefs about what's true. Paradigm shift occurs whenever there's a significant change in the way an individual or a group perceives something, and the old paradigm is replaced by a new way of thinking, or a new belief. Paradigm shift is an overarching assumption undergirding a general worldview. In the scientific community, this means the baseline beliefs about physics, biology, and other disciplines that experts take for granted as true. Scientists measure their experiments and observations in relation to these beliefs (Jibrilla, 2018).

In the present-day, paradigm shifts refer just as easily to surprising political outcomes or new artistic movements as they do to the arrival of a new baseline assumption and methodology in chemistry or astronomy. Still, the definition of paradigm shift remains the same no matter which field it crops up in: a radical change from previous prevailing attitudes that forms the basis of a new orthodoxy. Paradigm shifts happen by trickles of questioning and then in a flood of changes. Thomas Kuhn believed scientific research stays within a certain subset of beliefs (a scientific paradigm) most of the time. Scientists rely on these broad assumptions about the world and their field of study to do their work. Kuhn called this "normal science." But as time progresses, scientists occasionally discover new data that presents paradoxes or directly contradicts this dominant paradigm. These contradictions build and build until theoreticians arrive to make sense of them by proposing entirely new assumptions and beliefs, sweeping away the previous paradigm and replacing it with a new one (Johnson, S. & Nino-Zarazua, 2016). Paradigms are generally defined as a framework that has unwritten rules and that directs actions. A

paradigm shift occurs when one paradigm loses its influence and another takes over. The concept defines paradigm and paradigm shift and explains how it can relate to company strategies and industry cycles. A mature science, according to Kuhn, experiences alternating phases of normal science and revolutions. In normal science the key theories, instruments, values and metaphysical assumptions that comprise the disciplinary matrix are kept fixed, permitting the cumulative generation of puzzle-solutions, whereas in a scientific revolution the disciplinary matrix undergoes revision, in order to permit the solution of the more serious anomalous puzzles that disturbed the preceding period of normal science.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

The following theories underpinned this study

Swan Theory

The theory on which this study hinges is the theory of black swan. The black swan theory or theory of black swan events is a metaphor that describes an event that comes as a surprise, has a major effect, and is often inappropriately rationalised after the fact with the benefit of hindsight. Just like the case of the COVID-19 pandemic which came as a surprised and has affected the world economy in various ways; also affecting small and medium scale enterprises all over the world. There have been a number of Black Swan events throughout history and they can take very different forms. Both World Wars, the fall of the Soviet Union, the rise of Islamic fundamentalists, 9/11, the impact of the spread of the Internet, and the 1987 and 2008 financial crises are all examples of Black Swan events. But we are living through a Black Swan event right now.

There has been some debate over whether the coronavirus pandemic is a Black Swan, event while the threat of a virus was known, the unpreparedness of governments around the world shows it was considered an outlier event and that there was a low possibility it could happen. It has also had dire consequences, both on public health and the

economy. The COVID-19 pandemic has led to a dramatic loss of human life worldwide and presents an unprecedented challenge to public health, food systems and the world of work. The economic and social disruption caused by the pandemic is devastating: tens of millions of people are at risk of falling into extreme poverty, while the number of undernourished people, currently estimated at nearly 690 million, could increase by up to 132 million by the end of the year. Millions of enterprises face an existential threat particularly the small and medium scale enterprises.

Flu Theory

The extreme immunologic response to the 1918 pandemic virus could have made patients more susceptible to deadly secondary bacterial infections, according to two researchers who explained the rationale behind their hypotheses yesterday in a perspective piece in an early online edition of *Emerging Infectious Diseases* (EID). The authors who detailed the hypotheses are Dr G. Dennis Shanks, director of the Australian Army Malaria Research Institute, and Dr John Brundage, a physician and epidemiologist with the Armed Forces Health Surveillance Center in Silver Spring, Md. In September 2011, the same two authors published an epidemiologic analysis of naval medical records that suggested the first wave of the 1918 pandemic was caused by an antigenically distinct virus that left its hosts vulnerable to getting sick again in the second wave with infections that weren't lethal. However, another study published about the same time suggested that cases in the first and second waves of the 1918 pandemic looked much the same, and it found no evidence of viral mutations that would explain why the fall wave was so much more severe. The study was based on tissue samples from pandemic victims.

During the 1918 pandemic, illness rates were highest among children, but mortality was highest in young adults, a highly unusual pattern for influenza. Shanks and Brundage wrote that an analysis of who got sick

and when they became ill provides some useful clues that might help explain the unusual mortality curve. Their assertions hinge on their view that the first of the three pandemic waves was caused by a different virus, given that clinical patterns varied between the first two waves. A review of 1918 pandemic flu mortality rates in different populations suggests that exposure to bacterial pathogens played an important role, they wrote. For example, case-fatality rates from secondary pneumonia were highest in Australian and American soldiers with pandemic flu who were relatively new to their settings. The authors hypothesized that many people in 1918 had their second exposures to an immunodominant T-cell epitope that was present on both the internal protein of the 1918 pandemic strain and on a similar previous strain, such as the 1889 pandemic virus. The second exposure could have led to a pathologic immune response that made patients vulnerable to deadly secondary bacterial infections, which they said may have contributed to the highly lethal nature of the second 1918 pandemic wave. They also suggested that the pathologic responses made people vulnerable to bacteria that they had not been exposed to before, noting military recruits in new locations or soldiers crowded on troop ships would've had such exposures. Mortality rates were lower in people who had previous exposure in their occupational settings, such as military clinics, the article says.

Factors that led to high mortality during the 1918 pandemic, such as commercial and social isolation, no longer exist on a global scale, and most young adults are likely to be exposed to numerous viral and bacterial pathogens, according to Shanks and Brundage, who said their hypothesis may explain why the mortality rate for the 2009 H1N1 pandemic was relatively low. The hypothesis about the T-cell epitope may have some implications for the development of universal flu vaccines, since it would be important "to ensure that T-cell-mediated responses to future seasonal and pandemic strains are protective but not pathogenic," they wrote. In an

editorial that accompanied the report, Dr David Morens and Dr Jeffery Taubenberger wrote that Shanks and Brundage's hypotheses were thought-provoking, but they said that a higher percentage of people of all ages, not just young adults, experienced flu that led to secondary bacterial pneumonia in 1918. Both were coauthors of the recent study on tissue samples from 1918 pandemic victims and are with the National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases.

Empirical Review

According to Harapan, (2020), in early December 2019, an outbreak of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), caused by a novel severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), occurred in Wuhan City, Hubei Province, China. On January 30, 2020 the World Health Organization declared the outbreak as a Public Health Emergency of International Concern. As of February 14, 2020, 49,053 laboratory-confirmed and 1,381 deaths have been reported globally. Perceived risk of acquiring disease has led many governments to institute a variety of control measures. We conducted a literature review of publicly available information to summarize knowledge about the pathogen and the current epidemic. In this literature review, the causative agent, pathogenesis and immune responses, epidemiology, diagnosis, treatment and management of the disease, control and preventions strategies are all reviewed.

Pramath, (2020) review on basic sciences aims to clarify the jargon in virology, describe the virion structure of SARS-CoV-2 and present pertinent details relevant to clinical practice. Another component discussed is the brief history on the series of experiments used to explore the origins and evolution of the phylogeny of the viral genome of SARS-CoV-2. Additionally, the clinical and epidemiological differences between COVID-19 and other infections causing outbreaks (SARS, MERS, H1N1) are elucidated. Emphasis is placed on evidence-based medicine to evaluate the frequency of

presentation of various symptoms to create a stratification system of the most important epidemiological risk factors for COVID-19. These can be used to triage and expedite risk assessment. Furthermore, the limitations and statistical strength of the diagnostic tools currently in clinical practice are evaluated. Criteria on rapid screening, discharge from hospital and discontinuation of self-quarantine are clarified. Epidemiological factors influencing the rapid rate of spread of the SARS-CoV-2 virus are described.

Mohsin, (2020) study aims to assess the impact of COVID-19 outbreak on these businesses and provide policy recommendations to help MSMEs in reducing business losses and survive through the crisis. An exploratory methodology with comprehensively reviewing the available literature, including policy documents, research papers was adopted. Further, to add empirical evidence, data were 184 Pakistani MSMEs by administering an online questionnaire. The data were analyzed through descriptive statistics. The results indicate that most of the participating enterprises have been severely affected and they are facing several issues such as financial, supply chain disruption, decrease in demand, reduction in sales and profit, among others. Besides, over 83% of enterprises were neither prepared nor have any plan to handle such a situation. Further, more than two-thirds of participating enterprises reported that they could not survive if the lockdown lasts more than two months. The findings of our study are consistent with previous studies.

Mckibbin and Fernando (2020) study coronavirus pandemic in Nigeria: how can small and medium enterprises (smes) cope and flatten the curve. According to the authors the negative effect of the invisible enemy is ravaging the entire world populace, leading to global economic crisis. Businesses across the globe are feeling the negative impact of the coronavirus COVID-19 pandemic threatening their going concern status. SMEs in Nigeria are not left out

in the share of this negative effect of the invisible enemy, as their survival is being threatened and the government is not helping. We reviewed literature on the impact of COVID-19 on SMEs and subsequently proposed a model to help them win the fight alongside with the federal government in flattening the curve. We concluded that SMEs can triumph in this turbulent time following the laid down health advice, and we pray the world heals of this pandemic in no distant time.

Sharu and Guyo (2020) study was on COVID-19 impact on SMEs in Bangladesh: An Investigation of What they are experiencing and how they are managing. SMEs in Bangladesh have already been experiencing the devastating and ruthless impact as such the motivation of the study to develop insight relating to what is experiencing by SMEs and how they are managing.

This study used a descriptive analysis method of primary and secondary data obtained directly both from field survey and from various publication sources. The study findings might assist in formulating the strategic decision focusing on SMEs revival and growth after the pandemic become stable. Study findings also utterly established the fact i.e. government should invest considerable effects for mobilization and efficient reallocation of resources through collaboration of both Banks and nonbanks financial instructions. Else, unemployment, decline growth speed, and social insecurity might appear and prevail in the long run.

Tejal (2020) paper demonstrates the use of a linear Input-Output (IO) model to estimate the economic losses in India due to COVID-19. The results show that depending on the duration of the lockdown, the Indian economy is likely to face a loss of about 10e31% of its GDP. This method can be applied to assess economic losses for other regions also. The paper also discusses the impacts of COVID-19 on the demand and supply of electricity and CO₂ emissions from the

power sector. The results show that daily supply from coal-based power plants has reduced by 26% during the lockdown resulting in a possible emissions reduction of about 15e65 MtCO₂ depending on the lockdown duration. The cost of avoided carbon is approximately 186e264 \$/tCO₂, much higher than the \$7e12/tCO₂ currently being paid by consumers in India indicating the difficulty of achieving emissions reductions through restructuring economic activity as often advocated.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted with reference to the existing theoretical literature review. Published, unpublished, online journals and magazines by other researchers on similar research were critically examined to investigate the research problem. The qualitative approach provides perceptions to social components of the procedures amongst agencies (Denzin & Lincoln 2018). The qualitative technique is regarded as a suitable method to investigate the Post Covid-19 Paradigm Shift in Social Sciences, Technology and Public Health in Nigeria. The approach will assist the manner on which role players (beneficiaries, government, industries at large and policy makers) better understand the Paradigm Shift in Social Sciences, Technology and Public Health for proper policy recommendations.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The COVID-19 pandemic has created multiple paradigm shifts the likes of which organizations have never before seen. Even the most prepared organizations scrambled to react to the rapid changes brought on by the pandemic. Whereas most organizations would agree that technology, public health, social sciences and humanity such as (financial consequences, remote work, worker well-being, and career attitudes) have all shifted, organizations ability to understand and respond to those shifts in both the short- and long-term has become another story

altogether. However, by becoming more aware of these paradigm shifts in the key areas discussed above, practitioners can better position themselves to explore the myriad of organizational changes resulting from the pandemic. Furthermore, awareness of these paradigm shifts enables individuals and organizations to proactively adapt to a rapidly changing business environment. It is likely that the effects of this pandemic will need to be explored for years to come in order to truly understand the depth and magnitude of effect. By being armed with a knowledge of these paradigm shifts, their implications, and the issues for consideration, organizations and their leaders can take the actions that should lead to long-term organizational success. It is recommended that the government should grant tax breaks to companies seeking to increase their capacity to produce import substitute goods, which could even mean zero-rating VAT for the next 3-months; Releasing VAT refunds to assist businesses with managing their cash flow; Encouraging banks to give concessionary loans at low rates to facilitate businesses, and as well provide moratoriums on loans that are due; the government must ensure the equitable distribution of health care and other material support such as food, soap and water. Besides, community engagement is vital to increase access to information about control measures, address stigma surrounding COVID-19 and comply with the control measures; It is no news that the COVID-19 pandemic will disrupt the global and Nigerian economy in 2020. However, Nigeria can cushion the impact of the virus by introducing measures to protect companies and their workers, most especially the vulnerable citizens, from the impact of the quarantine measures. Such measures could include: Unemployment benefits, Employment retention, Social assistance benefits and financial support and tax relief.

REFERENCES

- Akindamola, S (2020). National Economic Consultative Forum. Report on the Policy Implementation Workshop For SMEs 25-27 January 2020.
- Al-Samarrai, S., P. Cerdan-Infantes and J. D. Lehe (2019). "Mobilizing Resources for Education and Improving Spending Effectiveness: Establishing Realistic Benchmarks Based on Past Trends." World Bank Policy Research Working Paper (8773).
- Antara, I. J. (2020). "COVID-19 Crisis Impact on RMG wages and employment and Role of Trade Unions." Dhaka, BRAC Institute of Governance and Development
- Harapan, G.Z. (2020). "The short-term impact of SARS on the Chinese economy", *Asian Economic Papers*, 3, (1), 31-49.
- ILO (2020). "ILO Monitor 2nd edition: COVID-19 and the world of work: Updated estimates and analysis." Geneva, International Labour Organization.
- IMF (2020). *World Economic Outlook: The Great Lockdown* (Chapter 1). Washington D.C., International Monetary Fund.
- Janet, M. & Ngugi, K . (2014). Influence of Entrepreneurial Marketing on The Growth of Smes In Kiambu Town-CBD, Kenya. *European Journal of Business Management*, 1(11), 361-377.
- Jibrilla, A.A. (2018). Impact of Government Interventions on Small Scale Entreprises in Mubi North Local Government Area, Adamawa State, Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 4(17), 121.
- Johnson, S. & Nino-Zarazua M. (2016). Financial Access and Exclusion in Kenya and Uganda. *The Journal of Development Studies*, 47(3), 475-96
- Letko, M.; Marzi, A.; & Munster, V. (2020) Functional assessment of cell entry and receptor usage for SARS-CoV-2 and other

- lineage B betacoronaviruses. *Nat. Microbiol.* 2020,5, 562–569.
- Lipsitch, M. (2020) Potential biases in estimating absolute and relative case-fatality risks during outbreaks. *PLoS Negl. Trop. Dis.* 2015,9.
- Loayza, N. V. & S. Pennings (2020). “Macroeconomic Policy in the Time of COVID-19: A Primer for Developing Countries.” Washington D.C., World Bank.
- Lu, H.; Stratton, C.W.; Tang, Y.W. (2020) Outbreak of pneumonia of unknown etiology in Wuhan, China: Themystery and the miracle. *J. Med. Virol.* 2020, 92, 401–402.
- Mahler, D., C. Lanker, R. Aguilar & H. Wu (2020). “The impact of COVID-19 (Corona-virus) on global poverty: Why Sub-Saharan Africa might be the region hardest hit.” Data Blog.
- Mckibbin, W. J., & Fernando, R., (2020). “The global macroeconomic impacts of Covid-19: Seven Scenarios”. Centre of Excellence in Population Ageing Research (CEPAR) Research Paper, 2 March, 2020; pp 1-43.
- Mohsin, Y. (2020). Fiscal and monetary policies: Challenges for small and medium enterprises (SMEs) development in Tanzania. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Entrepreneurship*, 1(10), 305-320.
- Peeri, N.C.; Shrestha, N.; Rahman, M.S.; Zaki, R.; Tan, Z.; Bibi, S.; Baghbanzadeh, M.; Aghamohammadi, N.; Zhang, W.; Haque, U. (2020) The SARS, MERS and novel coronavirus (COVID-19) epidemics, the newest and biggest global health threats: What lessons have we learned? *International Journal of Epidemiology*. 10, 14–25
- Pramath, C. (2020). National Economic Emancipation and Development Strategy (NEEDS): A Spring Board for Nigerian Sustainable Development. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review (Oman Chapter)*, 4(5), 23-32.
- Rahman, Z. & I. Matin (2020). “Livelihoods, Coping, and Support during Covid-19 Crisis.” Dhaka, BRAC Institute of Governance and Development.
- Sharu, H. & Guyo, W. (2020). Factors Influencing Growth of Youth Owned Small and Medium Enterprises in Nairobi County, Kenya. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 4(4), 973-987.
- UNESCO (2020). Global Education Monitoring Report: Migration, displacement and education. Paris, United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization.
- World Bank (2020). “COVID-19 Crisis: Through a Migration Lens.” Migration and Development Brief. Washington D.C., World Bank.
- World Health Organization (2020) Coronavirus Disease 2019 Situation Report. Available online: https://www.who.int/docs/default-source/coronaviruse/situation-reports/20200326-sitrep-66-covid-19.pdf?sfvrsn=9e5b8b48_2 (accessed on 25 March 2020).